

ID	Category	Short Description	Examples	Language Advocate	Project Manager	Team Leader	Crowdin Coordinator	Crowdin Translator	Crowdin Proofreader	Amara Coordinator	Amara Translator	Amara Proofreader	Content Specialist	Video editor	Dubber	Total
1	Platforms	Platforms that the problem occurs														
1.1.1	Crowdin	All the bottlenecks that occurs in Crowdin platform	"the title of the exercise does not match with the one in Khan Academy translation platform" (Crowdin translator, Interview 4)			1		1	1							3
1.1.2	Crowdin	All the bottlenecks that occurs in Crowdin platform	"Volunteers misuse the strings, and they damage it" (Crowdin Coordinator, Interview 4)	1				1								2
1.1.a	Smart translations	Smart translations might cause the massive error since it does not consider Azerbaijani grammar structure	"when I click "smart translations" button then it does not consider different suffixes that should be based on the number, and as a result I translate the entire upcoming translations wrong" (Crowdin Proofreader, Interview 4)					1	1	1		1	1			5
1.2.1	Amara	All the bottlenecks that occurs in Amara platform	"There not subtitles in English in the videos sometimes" (Amara translator, Interview 6)									1				1
1.2.2	Amara	All the bottlenecks that occurs in Amara platform	"It is hard to find videos on Amara" (Amara translator, Interview 6)	1	1						1	1	1			5
1.2.3	Amara	All the bottlenecks that occurs in Amara platform	"Screen texts are not translatable on Amara" (Language advocate, Interview 3)	1												1
1.3	KA database	All the bottlenecks that occurs in KA database	"Mapping is time-consuming, and it is hard for me to understand which videos are not unmapped when they were previously mapped" (Language Advocate, Interview 3)	1	1											2
Subprocesses of the localization process in which the bottlenecks occur																
2.1.1	Translate Crowdin content	Bootlenecks in "Translate Crowdin content" subprocess	"There are not enough proofreaders in the team" (Team leader, Interview 5)	1		1							1			3
2.1.2	Translate Crowdin content	Bootlenecks in "Translate Crowdin content" subprocess	"The quality of translation is quite different in Amara compared to Crowdin, it is much hard for the translator to localize this content" (Language Advocate, Interview 3)	1						1		1	1			4
2.2.1	Translate Amara content	Bootlenecks in "Translate Amara content" subprocess	"We lose a lot of time while solving the problems of translators, there are many people within this process" (Amara coordinator, Interview 8)		1			1			1	1			1	5
2.2.2	Translate Amara content	Bootlenecks in "Translate Amara content" subprocess	"Translators finish their tasks in a longer period compared to Crowdin" (Amara proofreader, Interview 4)							1			1	1		3
2.3	Control quality	Bootlenecks in "Control quality" subprocess	"Sometimes I need to edit the same video 3 times, and it takes too much time" (Video editor, Interview 9)												1	1
2.4	Deliver video	Bootlenecks in "Deliver video" subprocess	"Mapping is time-consuming, and it is hard for me to understand which videos are not unmapped when they were previously mapped" (Language Advocate, Interview 3)	1	1										1	3
Subprocesses of the localization process in which the stakeholders required a change because the "as is" process was not as it was designed																
3.1.1	Translate Crowdin Content	Edits about the mistake in "Translate Crowdin Content" subprocess	"After translating crowdin I do not tell to the team leader directly, I firstly tell to the Crowdin coordinator, and he tells to the team leader" (Crowdin translator, Interview 4)					1	1	1			1			4
3.1.2	Translate Crowdin	Edits about the mistake in "Translate Crowdin Content" subprocess	"Project manager never communicates with the translators" (Team leader, Interview 5)		1		1									2
3.2.1	Translate Amara content	Edits about the mistake in "Translate Amara Content" subprocess	"In case the problem occurs, I always get in touch with the coordinator, and she tells me what is the solution" (Amara translator, Interview 6)								1					1
3.3.1	Recreate videos	Edits about the mistake in "Recreate videos" subprocess	"When there is an error, then the video editor sends me back the audio, and I re-dub it" (Dubber, Interview 2)		1										1	2
3.3.2	Recreate videos	Edits about the mistake in "Recreate videos" subprocess	"Sometimes I wait for a long time to get the software key" (Video editor, Interview 9)												1	1
Subprocess optimization proposal																
4.1.1	General	Optimization proposals from the stakeholders about the general subprocess	"We can localize Crowdin and Amara paralely since they can be done so" (Langugage Advocate, Interview 11)	1						1		1				3
4.1.2	General	Optimization proposals from the stakeholders about the general subprocess	"It is better if the same volunteer translates the same content both in Amara and Crowdin" (Amara proofreader, Interview 12)										1			1
4.1.3	General	Optimization proposals from the stakeholders about the general subprocess	"It is better if the same volunteer proofreader the same content both in Amara and Crowdin" (Crowdin coordinator, Interview 12)	1	1	1	1	1		1				1		6
4.2.1	Translate Crowdin content	Optimization proposals from the stakeholders about the "Translate Crowdin content" subprocess	"Volunteers should be warned about using the strings on Crowdin in the beginning of the volunteering" (Crowdin coordinator, Interview 12)					1		1						2
4.2.2	Translate Crowdin content	Optimization proposals from the stakeholders about the "Translate Crowdin content" subprocess	"Sometimes coordinators, and sometimes project manager should be removed within the communication" (Crowdin coordinator, Interview 12)					1			1				1	3

